

AT ALL LEVELS OF THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM, ESPECIALLY
THE IMPORTANCE OF EDUCATING HIGHER SPIRITUAL, ETHICAL
AND EDUCATED STUDENTS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract

In this article, it is legal and necessary to give special importance to the education of students of higher educational institutions in all stages of the educational system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, especially in higher education, to be highly spiritual, moral and enlightened, and the principles and stages of its relevance were analytically described. It is important because it is directed to the field of improving the spiritual and moral qualities of student youth - that is, as an integral part of the complex social policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, employment in physical education and sports, the spiritual and moral qualities of student youth.

Key words: Key words: students, education, training, values, science, sports, culture, ethics and enlightenment, spirituality, freedom, free citizenship.

**НА ВСЕХ УРОВНЯХ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ,
ОСОБЕННО ВАЖНОСТЬ ВОСПИТАНИЯ ВЫСШИХ ДУХОВНЫХ,
ЭТИЧЕСКИХ И ОБРАЗОВАННЫХ СТУДЕНТОВ В ВУЗАХ.**

Аннотация

В данной статье правомерно и необходимо придать особое значение воспитанию студентов высших учебных заведений на всех ступенях системы образования Республики Узбекистан, особенно в высшем образовании, быть высокодуховными, нравственными и просвещенными, и аналитически

описаны принципы и этапы ее актуальности. Она важна, поскольку направлена в область совершенствования духовно-нравственных качеств студенческой молодежи – то есть как составная часть комплексной социальной политики Республики Узбекистан, занятость в сфере физического воспитания и спорта, духовно-нравственного воспитания. качества студенческой молодежи.

Ключевые слова: студенты, образование, подготовка, ценности, наука, спорт, культура, этика и просвещение, духовность, свобода, свободное гражданство.

**TA'LIM TIZIMINING BARCHA BOSQICHLARIDA, AYNIQSA,
OLIV TA'LIM MUASSASALARI TALABALARINI YUKSAK
MA'NAVIYATLI, AXLOQLI VA MA'RIFATLI QILIB TARBIYALASHGA
ALOHIDA AHAMIYAT BERISH DOLZARBLIGI**

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasi Ta'lim tizimining barcha bosqichlarida, ayniqsa, oliy ta'lim muassasalari talabalarini yuksak ma'naviyatli, axloqli va ma'rifatli qilib tarbiyalashga alohida ahamiyat berish qonuniy va zaruriy bo'lib, uning dolzarbligini rivojlantirish tamoyillari, bosqichlari tahliliy bayon etildi. Talaba yoshlarning ma'naviy-axloqiy sifatlarini- ya'ni O'zbekiston Respublikasi kompleks ijtimoiy siyosatining ajralmas qismi sifatida, jismoniy tarbiya va sport bilan bandlik, talaba yoshlarning ma'naviy-axloqiy sifatlarini oshirish sohasiga yo'naltirilganligi bilan muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Kalit so'zlar: Talabalar, ta'lim, tarbiya, qadriyat, ilm-fan, sport, madaniyat, axloq va ma'rifat, ma'naviyat, ozodlik, erkin fuqarolik.

**THE IMPORTANCE OF PAYING SPECIAL ATTENTION TO THE
EDUCATIONAL, MORAL AND ENLIGHTENED EDUCATION OF
STUDENTS AT ALL LEVELS OF THE EDUCATION SYSTEM,
ESPECIALLY IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS**

The introduction to the article refers to the Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5847 dated October 8, 2019 “On the Concept of Developing the Higher Education System until 2030” and “On Additional Measures to Further Improve the Education System of Our Country and Accelerate the Development of the Science and Technology Sector”

that aim to improve the quality and efficiency of the education system in the country, to provide young people with modern knowledge and skills, and to The need to implement systematic work on skills development, ensuring close cooperation and integration between education systems and the scientific community was recognized. Therefore, the organization, coordination, and management of pedagogical processes in higher education institutions make a significant contribution to ensuring the development of society based on the fulfillment of social obligations. In this regard, the development of moral and ethical qualities in students is considered important. Because globalization, as a force that promotes development, performs an integrative function in socio-economic processes, but at the same time, it is also a means of ideological influence. As a result of globalization, moral threats have emerged that lead to deviance and various criminal acts, which have become a serious threat to the security of humanity, the national interests of states, and the stable future of future generations. Representatives of the sociogenetic direction believe that the socialization of a person, the development of social norms and roles, the acquisition of social relations and value orientations, the formation of a person's The processes of formation of social and national character as a typical member of a certain community are studied. These problems are developed in social pedagogy and psychology, ethnopedagogy and psychology. The focus of the personogenetic direction is on the activities of the individual, self-understanding and creativity, self-esteem, the struggle of motives, the development of individual character and

abilities, the problems of self-realization of personal choice, and the tireless search for the meaning of life. It is legitimate and necessary to attach special importance to the upbringing of highly spiritual, moral, and enlightened students at all stages of the education system, especially students of higher educational institutions, and its relevance is explained by the following:

-firstly, with the independence of our country, the restoration and further enhancement of our great spirituality and its instillation in all citizens, first of all, in the youth, have been determined as a priority direction in our state policy, as in all spheres of our social life, at all stages of the education system, especially in higher educational institutions, as well as in all areas of our social life, to restore and further enhance our great spirituality, to strengthen its national and universal basis, to provide students and young people with knowledge and information based on the requirements of the time and world standards, and to instill and educate them with high spiritual culture, morality and enlightenment qualities;

-secondly, one of the most important tasks of our state is to educate a spiritually perfect person, to improve the education and enlightenment system, to bring up the younger generation spiritually and spiritually on the basis of the idea of national independence, and to interpret it on the basis of modern pedagogical technologies and an interactive approach.

-thirdly, the ongoing work to restore our national spirituality, the radical reform of public education in Uzbekistan, the emergence of the opportunity to educate socially active, spiritually mature individuals, to train qualified specialists for all spheres of the national economy, government agencies, science and technology and culture;

-fourthly, in the process of globalization associated with universal technologies, the education of young people with high spiritual and moral values is being carried out in the process of fierce ideological struggles. In this regard, the change in the

ideological system, social renewal require a new approach to, and view of, spiritual heritage.

Spirituality is a very broad concept, encompassing the concepts of enlightenment, culture, moral culture, socio-political, legal, and religious culture. "Spirituality is a powerful inner force that calls a person to spiritual purification and elevation, enriches a person's inner world, strengthens his faith, will, and conviction, and awakens his conscience". Indeed, spirituality is a person's spiritual As the sum of the universe, it provides spiritual nourishment and strength to man. Man They are not limited to material security, but live in pursuit of spirituality. Historical conditions or geographical, territorial proximity, if each nation is in close contact with its own nation, affect it and, in turn, are affected by it.

Cultural development is a continuous process, preserving national traditions, customs, and cultural heritage. During the development of each state and society, the new generation does not create its material and spiritual culture anew, but relies on the foundations of the material and spiritual culture left by its ancestors, accepts the wealth from its ancestors and continues them creatively. In order to create new values, it is necessary to master the spiritual heritage of its ancestors.

According to Sh. Abdullayeva, a scientist who studied the spiritual and moral qualities of young students in scientific research, "the spiritual and moral qualities of young students are formed in their communication with people, depending on the development of society, and the ability of the state to effectively manage spirituality and enlightenment. In this case, the level of spiritual and moral qualities develops".

The scientist G. Ibragimova, who contributed to the development of the moral qualities of students with her views, defined the concept of moral qualities as follows: "Moral qualities, as a social category, represent social relations of young people in the field of personal development in order to satisfy their personal and spiritual needs and realize their personal interests in development".

Vilensky M.Ya., A.G. Gorshkov defined “the development of spiritual and moral qualities as a system of relations resulting from the regularity of physical education and sports, as a result of the involvement of young people in sports and environmental activities”. Supporting this definition, Zakrevskaya N.G. defined “the development of spiritual and moral qualities as a set of social relations related to the creation of conditions for young people to engage in sports and their participation in sports”.¹

According to the scientist Yermakov V.A., who studied the problems of spiritual and moral qualities and sports, “the development of spiritual and moral qualities consists not only in the conditions created for young people to engage in physical education and sports, but also in the creation and provision of motivational factors necessary for their engagement.”

One of the pedagogical scientists, I.B. Akimov, states that the concept of “spiritual and moral qualities” should not be limited only to physical education and sports, and describes it as “spiritual and moral qualities are a type of social situation or social relations that include contradictions in the fact that young people regularly engage in sports and other activities, aimed at realizing their life goals, and the processes of engagement are not limited for one reason or another.” I.B. Akimov also defines “spiritual and moral qualities as the proportion of young people engaged in activities related to certain conditions of a certain normative level and scope existing in social life,” and believes that “spiritual and moral qualities are the actions of young people engaged in activities, developing their own thinking, and expressing the natural appearance of the life process of young people engaged in a certain activity, taking into account certain conditions of activities.” In the development of spiritual and moral qualities in students, the pedagogical process proceeds under certain conditions, the deficiency of any of its components violates the integrity of the

¹ Zakrevskaya N.G. *Zdorovyy obraz jizni i sotsialnoye zdorovye* / N.G. Zakrevskaya // *Sportivnaya deyatel'nost' v kontekste sotsialnogo zdorov'ya*. -Sankt-Peterburg, 2015. - S. 90-103.

pedagogical process, reduces its effectiveness. "In the pedagogical process, objective, socially subjective factors become the individual intellectual property of the student and ensure the development of the personality. Therefore, the pedagogical process is considered an organic unity of the processes of teaching, upbringing, education and development" [69, p. 41]. The tasks, content, methods and forms of the pedagogical process in a higher educational institution depend not only on the needs, but also on the capabilities of society, on the conditions in which this process takes place (material, hygienic, moral and psychological, etc.). The above-mentioned expression of the pedagogical process is associated with its external relations.

Spiritual wealth is a spiritual heritage created by the thinking and intelligence of many generations in the process of the development of human society. Spiritual wealth is a development that expresses ancient historical monuments. "From the most ancient inscriptions and writings created with the thought and genius of our ancestors, to the thousands of manuscripts kept in the treasures of our libraries today, and the invaluable works on history, literature, art, politics, ethics, philosophy, medicine, mathematics, mineralogy, chemistry, astronomy, architecture, agriculture and other fields embodied in them, are the greatest treasures of our great nation." "is our spiritual wealth" (30-31-b). For example, the priceless spiritual monument "Avesta" with a three-thousand-year history, the epic "Alpomish" - a unique masterpiece of folk oral creativity, the most beloved and revered holiday - Navruz, an inseparable part of our spirituality is our holy religion, our great ancestors Imam Bukhari, Imam Termizi, Imam Maturidi, Muhammad Musa Al-Khwarizmi, Al-Farghani, Ibn Sina, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Amir Temur, Mirzo Ulugbek, Alisher Navoi, Jadid The great spiritual - educational, scientific, social - philosophical heritage of our ancestors, the experience of statecraft, continues to serve the all-round development of our country, its bright future.

Moral duty is a development that expresses the high spiritual virtue inherent in a person, the reflection of his moral inclinations and desires in his feelings. Moral duty

can sometimes deprive a person of comfort and pleasures of life, and it is instilled in human thinking during the process of education or is accepted in the form of family and national traditions. A person's moral duty is a sense of moral debt to things, events and people who have had a positive impact on his spirituality, psyche, thinking, and played an important role in his upbringing. The great thinker Ibn Sina, in his "Treatise on Duty," defines duty as fulfilling a sense of indebtedness to God, a divine responsibility. The sense of spiritual duty has been formed and has been preserved on the basis of the several thousand-year history of our people, the practical experience of our great ancestors and forefathers. Therefore, by instilling this feeling in the minds and hearts of our students, we can contribute to the fundamental changes taking place in the life of our country. o'zgarishlarga daxldorlik hissini shakllantirish, Vatanimizning taraqqiy etishi va gullab-yashnashiga erishish mumkin.

Spiritual inheritance is a system that expresses the transmission of national and spiritual values, customs, traditions, ideas, experience, and knowledge from generation to generation, the variability of spirituality as a continuous process, and the inextricable connection of spiritual ties between generations. The mechanism of inheritance in different fields is unique: the criteria in art differ from those in science, and the situation in the natural sciences differs from that in the humanities. Inheritance can be manifested in local or global forms. If the local form of inheritance expresses professional, national, ethnic and other aspects of culture, then the universal form of spiritual inheritance is manifested in spiritual wealth, which has become the spiritual property of all humanity. For example, examples of material and spiritual heritage, such as the ancient Egyptian pyramids, Greek monuments, and the monuments of Timur and the Timurids, are considered the spiritual wealth of all humanity and are passed down from generation to generation. Our ancestors widely used all methods of oral folk art and art to pass on their heritage to future generations. With the development of technology and equipment, new effective methods of

spiritual inheritance have emerged: film, magnetic tape recording, stamping on a picture, storage in computer memory, etc. At different stages of social development, the possibilities of transmitting spiritual heritage from generation to generation based on hereditary traditions are determined by socio-economic, political, and ideological factors. Since the first days of independence, constant importance has been attached to the issue of enriching and widely disseminating the invaluable material and spiritual wealth created with the appreciation of our national values, history, spirituality, and great ancestors.

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